

DEVELOPING PUPILS' ENGLISH SPEAKING SKILL IN PRIMARY SCHOOL

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ABSTRACT

When talking about the formation and development of oral speaking skills in English primary school pupils, it is necessary to pay some attention to the issues of speech activity, the formation of human speech and the formation of speech in students. It is advisable to skip. The main function of language is to be a means of communication between people. A person develops speech throughout his life. This article is based on giving basic information about to enhance pupils' English speaking skills by using various methods, approaches and techniques. Today, many children are interested in learning different languages because it depends on global development in the world on education.

Pedagogical technology is the most optimal process of knowledge acquisition, using all the possibilities of human potential and technical means through the creation, application and unification of methods of teaching and learning. Psychological and methodological literature contains a number of concepts and many scientific articles on the formation and development of human speech. By matter, especially P.Ya. It is widely covered in the works of Galperin, Jinkin N.I., Leontev A.A, Zimnyaya I.A. and other well-known scientists. Of these, A.A. Leontev and I.A. It is worth mentioning the works of Zimnyaya. Because in their works, the stages of speech formation are analyzed from a

scientific point of view, they are connected with the methodology of foreign language teaching and serve as the basis for the method of foreign language teaching. (These concepts are explained). Since the analysis of the stages of speech formation and types of speech activities is not included in the task of this course work, we have chosen to cover more speech formation in younger children and their speech requirements.

From an early age, a person needs to speak, that is, to understand. As a child grows older, his or her need to express himself or herself will increase, and he or she will begin to use more and more complex language in his or her speech. This

means that a child's knowledge of a language is based on speech activity. Therefore, the formation and development of foreign language speaking skills in young children should be considered on a speech basis. Of course, there are many differences and differences between learning a native language and learning a foreign language.

For example, young learners who have just begun to learn a foreign language will have a mother tongue mechanism in place and will be able to express themselves fluently in their mother tongue. That's why the school pays more attention to the development of native language skills. In the teaching of a foreign language, first of all, it is necessary to form a speech mechanism based on the formation of existing speaking skills (here we are talking about the formation of a foreign language speech mechanism) and to work on the development of speaking skills required to go. But what is unique about both languages is the need for communication. It is well-known that spoken communication is based on certain symbols, words, phrases and speech constructions, which are different in different languages. This is why the role of the language environment in the development of speech is so great. In addition to mastering the spoken word, children expand their knowledge. In other words, their worldview develops in the process of speaking. This suggests that in order to develop students' speaking skills, as mentioned above, there is a need and a language environment, as well as a clear language material that requires them to develop a worldview. This means that the development of oral language in a foreign language also requires the selection of

language units and topics based on the age characteristics, interests, worldviews of students and the requirements for their upbringing.

Another important factor in developing students' oral skills is the development of speaking skills. It is well-known that speech skills are developed through the repetition of speech. To do this, you need to create a certain speaking environment and repeat the words and phrases you are learning over and over again.

Speech activity is a very wide range of activities. There are three things to keep in mind when it comes to shaping and growing:

1. Work on words;
2. Work on phrases or expressions;
3. Work on related speech.

The methodological literature shows that the teaching of foreign languages in high school is divided into three stages. It consists of three stages, covering grades 5-10. However, in recent years, the teaching system in the school system has become eleven years old, and the study of foreign languages begins in the second and third grades, and even in kindergarten. There is a big difference between the worldview and psychophysiological characteristics of students in grades 2-3-4 and students in grades 5-6. This suggests that the lesson should be organized with this in mind. In general, the specifics of each stage and their differences from other stages should be taken into account in the selection of teaching materials and the organization of the lesson. Therefore, the three levels of foreign language teaching in the given secondary school, which are currently

available in the methodological literature, will be supplemented by the stage covering 1-2-3-4 grades, and will include teaching in the secondary school. It can be interpreted as consisting of four stages. But it is a complex task that requires psychological and pedagogical study and experimentation.

Therefore, leaving this view as a hypothesis for the time being, we will try to cover the issues of oral speech development in the initial stage (grades 5-6) of this stage, based on the three stages given in the methodological literature.

As we come to the basic characteristics of the primary stage, it is known that in the first stage the "foundation" of learning English is created. In school, the difference between these stages is not clearly defined, and therefore the transition from one stage to another in the teaching process is gradual. Therefore, the boundary between the stages is considered to be the end of the academic year. In fact, the specifics of one stage may persist for a while.

As the first stage is the initial stage of foreign language teaching and learning, it also pays great attention to the development of oral speech and reading techniques. At this stage, it is important to teach pronunciation to understand foreign language speech, which is an element of the foreign language speech mechanism, and to use the simplest and simplest question-and-answer speech combinations in oral communication. In the first academic year, special attention should be paid to teaching English pronunciation, as it is during this period that pronunciation skills are formed and in the later stages it is expanded and developed. If students have a clear

pronunciation and articulation of English sounds in the beginning, it will be more difficult to solve this problem in the later stages. Because the correction of speech sounds requires special exercises and methods of work, it is necessary to spend more time at the upper level than at the lower level.

1. The most important task in the first stage is to learn to use the selected lexical material in speech based on certain grammatical structures. This contributes to the formation of the speech formation mechanism. It is necessary to achieve a high degree of automation of the studied grammatical structures. Lexical and grammatical limitations, which are specific to foreign language teaching in the first year, prevent the learning process from being organized on a specific thematic basis. In this way, it creates the conditions for the organization of the training at the initial stage on the basis of the topics that need to be studied in the later stages.

2. If we consider foreign language teaching at the initial stage by types of speech activities, it is necessary to perform the following tasks in their teaching:

- a) create a learning mechanism;
- (b) developing oral reading techniques;
- c) teaching them to understand what they are reading.

3. The peculiarity of this process is that it is carried out by reading aloud texts based on previously studied lexical-grammatical, grammatical material.

4. The development of written speech at the elementary level is characterized by the study of the spelling of words learned in oral English. According to the principle of oral advancement of foreign language

teaching, the study of language material is not carried out simultaneously in oral speech and reading. At this stage, the study of language material is carried out according to the following scheme: listening comprehension - speaking - reading - writing.

It is clear that in the initial stage, more attention is paid to the types of speech activities that have a verbal character. The term "oral introduction" is often used in the early stages of foreign language teaching. In the methodological literature (for example, in the works of Palmer and textbooks based on the Dexon series), this section is divided into 1-1.5, which is orally advanced. Some Methodists say that it is enough to cover 2-3 hours, while the rest of the time it is better to teach in a complex way. Since oral work is considered to be oral in nature, it is worthwhile to cover it more orally, as the work during this period consists mainly of:

1. To develop students' correct English pronunciation skills and to achieve the correct intonation of the grammatical structures of the language being studied.

2. With the selected lexical material to study grammatical structures in the process of listening comprehension and speaking and to study them at an early stage

to teach correct pronunciation and use in oral speech through complementary and question-and-answer exercises.

3. Some of it in the study of grammatical structures from lexical units

Use as a groundbreaking tool to explore other types of speaking activities using substitute exercises to create different sentences by substituting parts

4. Learn how to write and read English letters, letter units in an introductory course in the English alphabet. Although the introductory course will include English syllables, letter combinations, and some words and phrases does not contradict the principle of oral advancement, as the writing and reading skills acquired by students during this period only serve as a preparation for mastering these types of speaking activities.

In the beginning, there is a lot of space for reading aloud. Reading texts have also become more and more complex, from the simplest to the simplest. However, it should be noted that although the work in the early stages is mainly focused on the development of oral skills, it does not solve the problem of developing oral skills in English. She is only preparing to work on a real speech. The main difficulty in working on oral speech at this stage is when students have mastered certain lexical units that allow them to compose not only individual sentences but also related sentences.

In addition, students will be introduced to The Present in Definite Tense. , The Future Tense in definite Tense is required to be familiar with verb tenses and to be able to use verb forms vividly in these tenses. Students will be introduced to the use of nouns in the singular and the plural, the addition of the suffix "s" or "es" to the third person singular form of a verb that has just arrived in the indefinite tense, and the interrogative, negative, and imperative forms of sentences. during the study period. If students can't answer simple questions and they only speak using the same grammatical construction, we

shouldn't take their speech as real English speech. Also, answering simple questions does not mean speaking English.

In this case, both character exercises and oral speech development exercises should focus on the following tasks and the main focus of the foreign language learning activity at this stage and on the English language learning by the students.

-Working on and mastering English pronunciation involves the sound and intonation structure of students' speech. Attention to students' pronunciation in English should not be diminished during this period.

-Reading is often accompanied by distortions in the articulation of sounds formed in oral speech. This should be avoided and additional oral exercises should be performed if necessary.

-Learning new words is based on previously learned graphic constructions. This allows the simplest communication to be measured by the one who forms the speech mechanism based on the material selected for this stage, and allows the listener to understand and speak English in the future. Understand what you are reading and master the technique.

-Reading skills are developed based on words learned in oral speech. Spelling of words learned in students' oral speech conduct research based on written exercises and reinforce the lexical and grammatical material learned through writing. In the early stages, listening, listening comprehension, and speaking are taught through the practice of using grammatical structures in speech.

Oral training. Oral communication is taught through listening, listening and speaking. Here, the speaker engages in

verbal communication in the process of conveying information, while the listener engages in verbal communication through listening and understanding it. During the conversation, the roles and positions of the speaker and the listener alternate, ie they can take turns listening and speaking. Oral communication can be one-sided. In this case, the first person only speaks, and the second listens. This type of speech is called one-way speech. The form of speech in which the speaker and the listener alternate is called "dialogic" speech. A monologue is a reference monologue given by a person. It can be broadcast in radio mode. The monologue has its own characteristics, which include: Before a monologue, the more you say, the less you want. Monolithic speech has a linguistic grammatical structure. In monologue speech, great emphasis is placed on pronunciation. There are the following types of monologue:

- a) The story
- b) Description
- c) Description
- d) Discussion
- e) Report

Some Methodist scholars also consider Retell to be a type of monologue speech. Because one person participates in the speech. But other scholars believe that Retell is not a monologue because he lacks the ability to express himself. Monologic speech occurs with or without preparation. We will use an introductory monologue. Unprepared monologues are intended for the upper grades and include:

1. Think of a topic and explain it.
2. Describe the pictures.
3. Create a situation based on previously learned information.

4. Explain the differences.
5. Brief announcement.
6. Dialogic speech.

Dialogic speech is a type of oral speech that is based on a conversation between two or more people. The Methodist says that when a subject begins to teach a foreign language, it is first necessary to develop dialogic speaking skills and competencies. We need to create a speech situation before we can develop a dialogic speech. There are two types of speech situations:

1. Natural

2. Educational Psychological

features of dialogic speech: 1. More than one person participates. 2. Always be prepared for the interlocutor's question. 3. Focuses on a specific person. 4. Speech situation plays a big role. 5. Dialogic speech is characterized by emotionality. 6. Dialogic speech requires a certain motivation and initiative.

Linguistic features of dialogic speech:

1. Question and answer unit.
2. The presence of different bites.
3. The presence of extralinguistic phage.
4. The presence of short and incomplete sentences.
5. Frequent use of standard or typological words.

Common dialog units are:

1. Report, fill in the message.
2. Communicate, express your opinion.
3. Ask again after the message.
4. Reporting.
5. Asking questions is punishing.
6. Ask a counter-question.
7. Command - approval.

8. Please - report.

9. Command - to express one's opinion.

In addition, there are some essential ways of developing students' speaking skills

-Developing fluency in spoken English.

-Focus on student needs.

-Provide relevant input.

-Teach common language chunks and phrases.

-Focus on fluency.

-The importance of pronunciation.

-Implementing feedback during speaking activities.

-Final thoughts.

In conclusion, speaking is a fundamental language skill. It is the primary way in which we communicate information. When we ask how well we can function in a second language, we ask the question "how well do you speak...?", so it is the ability to speak well which best represents our proficiency in another language. As teachers, however, we must be mindful that speaking involves more than simply using words to articulate what we are thinking, and there is more at play than simply asking students to say the words that they know. So, when planning a speaking skills lesson, be aware that using language in speech is not necessarily practice of speaking as a language skill. Developing the range of competencies that make 'a good speaker' takes focus on the ways that we speak to different people, and the ways we construct what we are saying. This is independent from the grammar and vocabulary we use in real life, so should be kept separate from pure language input in the language classroom.

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